

The Hydraulic Performance of Cylindrical Chamber Trap with Different Baskets Blockage Conditions

Author Details: Mohamed S ISMAIL

School of Engineering, Edith Cowan University 270 Joondalup Dr. Joondalup 6027 WA

Abstract:

The effect of different baskets conditions on stormwater cylindrical chamber trap (CCT) performance has been experimentally investigated using two different perforated baskets, round and square. With the two different baskets, 0%, 25%, 50% and 75% basket blockage conditions are tested. The results show that the head loss increases proportionally with the increase of flow rate and basket blockage conditions. The head loss coefficient is also obtained to increase with the increase of basket blockage percentages. Data analysis shows that there is no significant change between round and square baskets. Water level and Re number are also presented. This paper is a continues work which has been published by Ismail in 2016.

Keywords: Head loss, Head loss coefficient, Basket blockage conditions

Introduction:

The cylindrical chamber trap is an underground device designed to capture gross pollutants from stormwater drainage systems before they are released to natural watercourses. This paper is presenting in detail the hydraulics characteristic such as head loss, head loss coefficient and water level of the flow throughout the internal/treatment chamber. Numerous studies have been experimentally and numerically performed for the effect of geometrical parameters on the flow pattern and performance but the effect of basket blockage conditions is rarely investigated. These studies are presenting the effect of the flow rates versus head loss or trapping efficiency of scale models on cylindrical chamber traps without sufficient details about the effects on basket blockage conditions. The new trend is to investigate the hydraulic characteristics via multi-basket conditions.

Ismail et al., 2006 and Ismail et al., 2007 performed experimental studies on stormwater traps for the effect of basket blockage conditions. They have reported that the head loss/pressure drop increases proportionally with the flow rate. It is also proved that the pressure drop raises up with the increase of the blockage conditions. The stormwater trap scale model was VersaTrap type G (VTG). As VTG has designed to have a bypass, five different basket blockage conditions (0, 25, 50, 75 and 100%) have been achieved. The highest pressure drop was found 245mm on 100% condition at 20l/s. The head loss coefficient values at the first four basket conditions are ranging fairly from 1.89 at 0% up to 2.41 at 75%, which is a reasonable value compared to GPT's used around Australia (Ismail et al. 2006).

Ismail & Nikraz, 2008 investigated the performance of Rocla VersaTrap type A (VTA). Similar to VTG, the VTA trap was designed for gross stormwater pollutants and tested at four selected basket conditions. The study has found that the head loss at 10 l/s was different, 305mm at 0% and 330mm at 75% basket condition. Due to the complicity of the VTA model geometry, VTA has higher head loss values compared to VTG. As expected, the VTA head loss coefficient (K_e) was about 4 which is twice than of VTG's K_e .

Ismail, 2016 started conducting and testing the cylindrical chamber trap (CCT) model without installing basket/s. the study was focused on the hydraulic characteristics and trapping efficiency at selected flow rates. It was found that the head loss is increasing with the increase of flow rate. It starts from the lowest value 5mm at 2.5l/s to 70mm at 15l/s. Although the scale model has been tested without basket/s, the head loss coefficient was found 2. Similarly, the water level was found to increase proportionally with the flow rate to achieve the maximum 810mm at 15l/s.

Experimental Test Procedure:

Graphical representations of the CCT model and setup are presented in figures 1 and 2. The test procedure was exactly performed similarly to the study of Ismail in 2016. Water was pumped to the CCT model via a three-phase

pump and the flow rate was controlled by a speed controller unit and valve. Pressure head at inlet/outlet pipes are measured by a manometer and water levels are achieved using a steel ruler. The hydraulic tests involved the determination of treatment flows and the corresponding head losses with both baskets at 0, 25, 50 and 75% basket blockage conditions. This was carried to represent the actual basket condition in the field (Ismail & Nikraz 2008). Figure 3 shows the 5mm perforated round and square baskets at 75% basket blocked condition.

Figure 1: Cylindrical Chamber Trap

Figure 2 Experimental Setup Diagram (Ismail, 2016)

Figure 3: Round & Square 5mm Perforated Baskets at 75% Blockage Condition

Results and Discussion:

Head loss:

As CCT is designed for gross stormwater pollutants in commercial and industrial areas, more comprehensive tests were performed to establish true hydraulic characteristics. Head loss, head loss coefficient, water level, Reynolds number at the selected basket conditions have been achieved at each flow rate. As shown in figures 4 & 5, the head loss increases with the increase of the inlet velocities to reach the maximum 90mm at 16l/s (0.9m/s). This was found when round and square baskets were used at 0% blockage condition (figure 6). The head loss was also found to increase with the increase of screen blockage conditions. In both baskets, there were no significant changes in head loss and head loss coefficient at the first three basket conditions, 0%, 25% and 50%. At 75% basket condition, the head loss was reached the highest 153mm for the round basket and 140mm for the square basket at 16l/s (figure 7).

Figure 4: Relationship Between Head loss/Head loss Coefficient and Flow Rate at 0% Blockage Condition – Round Basket

Figure 5: Relationship Between Head loss/Head loss Coefficient and Flow Rate at 0% Blockage Condition – Square Basket

Figure 6: Relationship Between Head loss/Head loss Coefficient and Flow Rate at 0% Blockage Condition – Round, Square and Without Basket

Figure 7: Relationship Between Head loss and Flow Rate at 0% & 75% Blockage Condition – Round and Square Baskets

Head loss Coefficient:

The head loss coefficient (K_e) is used to show the performance of the hydraulic characteristics of gross pollutant traps. A low head loss coefficient makes the trap unit suitable for urban locations with low lying areas (Ismail et al.,

2006). The head loss coefficient was determined by calculating the ratio of energy loss to the equivalent full pipe velocity head at the inlet pipe. The calculations found that the coefficient to be the highest at low inlet velocity. From figures 4, 5 and 6, the value of the head loss coefficient decreases with the increasing flow rates and approaches a constant of 2.2 with 0% basket blockage condition. Comparing to VersaTraps, this value is slightly higher than VersaTrap type G coefficient 1.9 and much lower than VersaTrap type A coefficient 4. In both baskets, it was also found to increase as the blockage conditions increase to reach 3.6 at 75% condition for the round basket and 3.3 for the square basket. As expected, the head loss coefficient with round perforated basket is found higher and this of course, due to the cross-section area (figure 8).

Figure 8: Head loss Coefficient VS Basket Blockage Condition in Both Baskets

Water levels:

The water level has been measured at nine different locations (figure 9), five of them in the internal chamber. Figure 10 shows the water level at three points, 1, 5 and 9 without installing any baskets. It is found to increase proportionally with the increase of flow rate. The highest level is observed at point 1, where more pressure is expected; however, the lowest is shown at point 5 (centre of internal chamber). This is because of the vortex phenomena that cause the water level to decrease in the middle while the flow is directed tangentially into the chamber. With both baskets, the water level is accomplished at all basket blockage conditions and found to increase proportionally with the increase of blockage conditions (figure 11). Figures 12 and 13 proves no significant difference between water levels in the two baskets.

Figure 9: Locations for Water Level Measurement Points

Figure 10: Water Level - Without Basket

Figure 11: Water Level at all Points

Figure 12: Water Level at 75% Blocked - Round Basket

Figure 13: Water Level at 75% Blocked - Square Basket

Reynolds Number:

Laminar and turbulent flow can be characterised by calculating the Reynolds number (Munson et al., 2013). It is the ratio of inertial to viscous forces. At low inlet velocities, the flow is laminar but as the flow rate increases, turbulent flow is developed. Figure 14 shows the Reynolds number increases with the increase of flow rates and basket blockage conditions in both baskets. Reynolds number is very important for describing the transportation of a particle moving in a fluid (Rapp, 2017). A high Reynolds number in the system means fine particles with high inertia are unlikely to be trapped.

Figure 14: Reynolds Number at all Flow Rates

Conclusion:

The objectives of this paper were to determine and analyse in detail the hydraulic characteristics of the cylindrical chamber trap (CCT) with two different baskets. In 2016, the CCT model was experimentally tested without a treatment basket/s. This time, the model has been tested with a round and square perforated baskets at four different basket blockage conditions. The study proves that both baskets with 5mm perforated holes have achieved very similar performance. The head loss and head loss coefficient were found to increase in proportion with flow rates and basket blockage conditions. The head loss coefficient is acceptable for the first three blockage conditions; however, it is high at 75% condition. Water levels were measured for each flow rate and found the maximum 852mm in the round basket at a 75% blockage condition. This means CCT will still have the capability to capture floatable pollutants although Reynolds number shows very high turbulence to reach over 150000, which leads the fine particles to escape from the basket.

Future Work:

The next paper will be focused on numerical or CFD analysis at all selected basket conditions. Using one of the most powerful soft wares such as ANSYS, it is easy to obtain velocity and pressure profiles at any level inside the treatment chamber. The trapping efficiency can also be determined at each flow rate.

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